

An Evaluation of the Various Factors Affecting Medication Adherence in Diabetes Mellitus Patients: Observational Study

Shatrughan Kumar¹, MD. Tarique Anwar²

¹Department of Medicine, Specialist Medical Officer, Sadar Hospital, Motihari, Bihar, India

²Department of Medicine, Specialist Medical Officer, Sadar Hospital, Motihari, Bihar, India

Received: 12-08-2022 / Revised: 05-09-2022 / Accepted: 21-09-2022

Corresponding author: Dr. MD.Tarique Anwar

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Aim: The aim of the present study was to find out the modifiable risk factors which are responsible for the non- adherence among the diabetes population.

Methods: The present study was conducted in the Department of Medicine, Sadar Hospital, Motihari, Bihar, India for the period of 5 months. 400 patients were included in the study. Responses were recorded using a detailed questionnaire consisting of 25 questions. Responses were recorded in terms of Yes or No along with the basic demographic details.

Results: Of the 400 patients, majority were T2DM patients 380 (95%) followed by T1DM 10 (2.5%). Only 70 (17.5%) patients had family history of diabetes. Majority of the patients were illiterate 100 (25%) followed by 90 (22.5%) patients who were graduate. Majority of the patients were married 360 (90%), were businessman 110 (27.5%) and had monthly income between 5001 to 15000 rupees 90 (22.5%). Majority of the patients were on oral antidiabetic medications 300 (75%) followed by Ayurvedic plus Oral Antidiabetic medication 80 (20%). Only, 20 (5%) patients were on insulins.

Conclusion: For effective diabetes management medication adherence plays a very important role. Authors found a low level of medication adherence among the study population. This finding highlights the importance of improving the physician's approach on the modifiable risk factors on individual basis. However, it is the patients and their family who play a vital role in the diabetes management.

Keywords: Diabetes complications, Diabetes mellitus, Modifiable risk factors, Side effects

This is an Open Access article that uses a fund-ing model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

The incidence and prevalence of diabetes mellitus (DM) have continued to increase globally, despite a great deal of research, with the resulting burden resting more heavily on tropical, developing countries. [1,2] Type 2 DM, which is the more common of two basic types of DM, is increasingly being recognized in relatively

young persons, due to the high prevalence of environmental and genetic risk factors. [2]

Medication adherence refers to the extent to which patients take their medication regimen as prescribed by their health care provider. [3] A previous study suggests that about a quarter of patients are

nonadherent, and that rates of adherence are higher among patients with acute conditions than in those with chronic conditions. [4] Even in the resource-intensive setting of clinical trials, the average adherence rates for trial drugs used in chronic diseases are between 43% and 78%. [5-7]

Previous reports have shown that medication non-adherence is common among the type 2 diabetes patients (T2DM). [9] Poor adherence can compromise safety and treatment effectiveness which can lead to increase in diabetes related complications. [10,11] A report from the WHO has highlighted the importance of improving adherence to existing treatment in comparison to developing the new medical treatment. [8] Previous studies have explored the unmodifiable risk factors such as age, sex, ethnicity, income, education and comorbidities as the reasons for non-adherence. [12]

It is predicted that prevalence of DM in adults will increase in the next two decades and much of the increase will occur in developing countries where the majority of patients are aged between 45 and 64. [13,14]

With the current trend of transition from communicable to non-communicable diseases, it is projected that the latter will equal or even exceed the former in developing nations, thus culminating in double burden. [15,16] Type 2 DM is the most prevalent form of diabetes mellitus and accounts for about 90% of cases of diabetes. [17]

The aim of the present study was to find out the modifiable risk factors which are responsible for the non-adherence among the diabetes population.

Methods

The present study was conducted in the Department of Medicine, Sadar Hospital, Motihari, Bihar, India for the period of 5 months. 400 patients were included in the study. Responses were recorded using a detailed questionnaire consisting of 25 questions. Responses were recorded in terms of Yes or No along with the basic demographic details.

Inclusion criteria

- All diabetes patients (both Type 1 and type 2) having age more than 18 years and who were on diabetes medication were included.

Exclusion criteria

- Diabetes patients having age <18 years and suffering from serious complication and require hospitalization were excluded from the present study.

A detailed questionnaire consisting of 25 questions which included demographic details and the questions on the reasons for the treatment interruption were given to all the patients visiting to study center.

Methodology

Patients responded yes or no to each of the following questions: do you have financial problem, do you have no one to accompany you for visit, is diabetes medicine available in your area, do you find sufficient time to come for visit, are you busy in family obligation, is your medication lead to side effects, are you aware about the consequences of missing the doses, do you find it good to take long life medications.

All the data analysis was performed using IBM SPSS ver. 20 software. Frequency distribution was used for preparing tables. Quantitative data was expressed as mean±standard deviation whereas categorical data is expressed as percentage.

Results

Table 1: Factors responsible for the treatment interruptions among diabetes patients

Response (patients who had "Yes")	N	%
Financial problem	230	57.5
No one to accompany for visit	100	25
Non availability of medicines in his area	80	20
Lack of time to come for visit	180	45
Busy in family obligation	90	22.5
Shifted to alternative treatment	190	47.5
Side effects of medication	280	70
Not aware of the consequences of missing the doses	290	72.5
Long life medication period	300	75
Lack of awareness to take medication	270	67.5

Mean age, weight, height and BMI of study cohort was 48.62±10.12 years, 67.93±12.08 kgs, 163.75±8.08cm and 25.35±4.06kg/m² respectively. Majority of the patients were males 336 (68.4%).

Of the 400 patients, majority were T2DM patients 380 (95%) followed by T1DM 10 (2.5%). Only 70 (17.5%) patients had family history of diabetes. Majority of the patients were illiterate 100 (25%) followed by 90 (22.5%) patients who were graduate. Majority of the patients were married 360 (90%), were businessman 110 (27.5%) and had monthly income between 5001 to 15000 rupees 90 (22.5%). Majority of the patients were on oral antidiabetic medications 300 (75%) followed by Ayurvedic plus Oral Antidiabetic medication 80 (20%). Only, 20 (5%) patients were on insulins.

In present study majority of the patients were off the treatment for 1-5 months 300 (75%) followed by 40 (10%) patients who were off the treatment for 6-10 months.

Discussion

During the past three decades, the number of people with diabetes mellitus has continued to increase globally [18], and patients with type 2 diabetes (T2D) account for more than 90% of all patients with diabetes. [19] As a complex and chronic disease, T2D not only brings serious physical and psychological distress to both patients and caregivers [19] but also causes a large economic burden to society. [20] Therefore, the prevention and

treatment of T2D is particularly important. Guidelines recommend that most patients with T2D should receive appropriate medical care when lifestyle changes can no longer achieve metabolic control. [21,22] Current evidence shows that intensive antihyperglycemic therapy can effectively reduce the incidence of diabetes complications and death. [23] Therefore, medication adherence is important for achieving the treatment effect. [24]

Medication adherence is the important element of self-management for patients with diabetes mellitus. [6] Uncontrolled hyperglycemia can result in micro- and macrovascular complications such as retinopathy, nephropathy, neuropathy and associated cardiovascular diseases. For achieving a good glycemic control in diabetes patients, a right treatment and its strict adherence is very important. [25]

In present study authors observed male preponderance (70%) among diabetes patients which is hand in hand with the study done by Ascher-Svanum et al, where more than half of the enrolled diabetes patients were males (54%). Contrary to present study Awodele et al, reported female preponderance. [26,27]

Mojtabai et al, also reported that 7% of the patients were finding difficulties in purchasing medication due to the cost. [28] Awodele et al, also reported that more than half of the patients found their medication

unaffordable. [27] These findings are in agreement to the present study findings were more than half of the patients responded to have financial problem because of that they were finding difficulty in purchasing diabetic medication. In entered study, financial difficulties were one of the key factor influencing the non-adherence among diabetes patients. [29]

In present study majority of the patients were illiterate. This shows a low level of skills in the study population. Due to that the possibility of getting an employment is less when the qualification is low. The significance of lower income among the study cohort is the reason for not sustaining the cost of diabetes medication. In present study lack of awareness to take medication was another reason for the treatment interruption which may be due to the forgetfulness to take the medicine on time. In agreement to this study done by Lawton et al, who found that non-adherence was more related to patient forgetfulness than to specific concerns about medications or interaction with the physicians. [30]

Risk factors for poor adherence can be distinguished as unmodifiable factors such as age and sex and factors such as education, financial difficulties and presence of professional activity can be hardly modified in contest to medical relationship. [31] There are some modifiable risk factors such as family support, lack of information related to medication, and poor acceptability of medical recommendations on which treating physician could focus more in order to improve the medications adherence and in result could improve the glycaemic control.

Conclusion

For effective diabetes management medication adherence plays a very important role. Authors found a low level of medication adherence among the study population. This finding highlight the

importance of improving the physicians approach on the modifiable risk factors on individual basis. However, it is the patients and their family who play a vital role in the diabetes management. It is very important to develop knowledge and appropriate skills by the patients; also behavioral change is very important. By improving the risk factors for the poor adherence on individual basis better outcome can be obtained in terms of better glycemic control among the diabetes patients. We also elucidated the effect of adherence on achievement of satisfactory HbA1c levels at the observation endpoint. Because maintaining medication adherence and achieving HbA1c targets are important in reducing the likelihood of diabetic complications, targeted interventions for different groups—such as those of younger age and taking fewer medications—need to be developed. To conclude it is very important to identify the patients with poor adherence in order to improve the factors responsible.

References

1. Wild S, Roglic G, Green A, Sicree R, King H. Global prevalence of diabetes: estimates for the year 2000 and projections for 2030. *Diabetes Care*. 2004; 27(5): 1047–53.
2. Lindgren CM, Hirschhorn JN. The genetics of type II DM. *Endocrinologist*. 2001; 11:178-87.
3. Osterberg L, Blaschke T. Adherence to medication. *New England journal of medicine*. 2005 Aug 4;353(5):487-97.
4. DiMatteo MR. Variations in patients' adherence to medical recommendations: a quantitative review of 50 years of research. *Medical care*. 2004 Mar 1:200-9.
5. Cramer J, Rosenheck R, Kirk G, Krol W, Krystal J, VA Naltrexone Study Group 425. Medication compliance feedback and monitoring in a clinical trial: predictors and outcomes. *Value in Health*. 2003 Sep;6(5):566-73.

6. Waeber B, Leonetti G, Kolloch R, McInnes GT, HOT study group. Compliance with aspirin or placebo in the Hypertension Optimal Treatment (HOT) study. *Journal of hypertension*. 1999 Jul 1;17(7):1041-5.
7. Claxton AJ, Cramer J, Pierce C. A systematic review of the associations between dose regimens and medication compliance. *Clinical therapeutics*. 2001 Aug 1;23(8):1296-310.
8. World Health Organization. Adherence to long-term therapies: evidence for action. World Health Organization; 2003.
9. Cramer JA. A systematic review of adherence with medications for diabetes. *Diabetes Care* 2004; 27(5): 1218-24.
10. Sokol MC, McGuigan KA, Verbrugge RR, Epstein RS. Impact of medication adherence on hospitalization risk and healthcare cost. *Medical care*. 2005 Jun 1:521-30.
11. Lee WC, Balu S, Cobden D, Joshi AV, Pashos CL. Prevalence and economic consequences of medication adherence in diabetes: a systematic literature review. *Manag Care Interface*. 2006; 19(7):31-41.
12. DiMatteo MR. Variations in patients' adherence to medical recommendations: a quantitative review of 50 years of research. *Medical care*. 2004 Mar 1:200-9.
13. Murray CJ, Lopez AD. Alternative projections of mortality and disability by cause 1990–2020: Global Burden of Disease Study. *The lancet*. 1997 May 24;349(9064):1498-504.
14. Shaw JE, Sicree RA, Zimmet PZ. Global estimates of the prevalence of diabetes for 2010 and 2030. *Diabetes research and clinical practice*. 2010 Jan 1;87(1):4-14.
15. Yach D, Hawkes C, Gould CL, Hofman KJ. The global burden of chronic diseases: overcoming impediments to prevention and control. *Jama*. 2004 Jun 2;291(21):2616-22.
16. Magnusson RS. Non-communicable diseases and global health governance: enhancing global processes to improve health development. *Globalization and Health*. 2007 Dec;3(1):1-6.
17. World Health Organization. Diabetes action now: an initiative of the World Health Organization and the International Diabetes Federation.
18. Zheng Y, Ley SH, Hu FB. Global aetiology and epidemiology of type 2 diabetes mellitus and its complications. *Nature reviews endocrinology*. 2018 Feb;14(2):88-98.
19. Chatterjee S, Khunti K, Davies MJ. Type 2 diabetes. *The lancet*. 2017 Jun 3;389(10085):2239-51.
20. Seuring T, Archangelidi O, Suhrcke M. The economic costs of type 2 diabetes: a global systematic review. *Pharmacoeconomics*. 2015 Aug; 33(8): 811-31.
21. Jia W, Weng J, Zhu D, Ji L, Lu J, Zhou Z, Zou D, Guo L, Ji Q, Chen L, Chen L. Standards of medical care for type 2 diabetes in China 2019. *Diabetes/metabolism research and reviews*. 2019 Sep;35(6):e3158.
22. Doyle-Delgado K, Chamberlain JJ, Shubrook JH, Skolnik N, Trujillo J. Pharmacologic approaches to glycemic treatment of type 2 diabetes: synopsis of the 2020 American diabetes association's standards of medical care in diabetes clinical guideline. *Annals of internal medicine*. 2020 Nov 17;173(10):813-21.
23. Holman RR, Paul SJ, Bethel MA. coll. Ten years follow up of intensive glucose control in type 3 diabetes. *N Engl J Med*. 2008.
24. Lin LK, Sun Y, Heng BH, Chew DE, Chong PN. Medication adherence and glycemic control among newly diagnosed diabetes patients. *BMJ Open Diabetes Research and Care*. 2017 Jul 1;5(1):e000429.
25. Pollack MF, Purayidathil FW, Bolge SC, Williams SA. Patient-reported tolerability issues with oral antidiabetic

- agents: Associations with adherence; treatment satisfaction and health-related quality of life. *Diabetes Res Clin Pract.* 2010;87(2):204-10.
26. Ascher-Svanum H, Lage MJ, Perez-Nieves M, Reaney MD, Lorraine J, Rodriguez A et al. Early Discontinuation and Restart of Insulin in the Treatment of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus. *Diabetes Ther.* 2014;5(1):225-42.
27. Awodele O, Osulale JA. Medication adherence in type 2 diabetes patients: study of patients in Alimosho General Hospital, Igando, Lagos, Nigeria. *African Health Sciences.* 2015;15 (2): 513-22.
28. Mojtabai R, Olfson M. Medication Costs, Adherence and Health Outcomes Among Medicare Beneficiaries. *Health Aff.* 2003;22 (4): 220-9.
29. Tiv M, Viel J-F, Mauny F, Eschwe`ge E, Weill A, et al. Medication Adherence in Type 2 Diabetes: The ENTRED Study 2007, a French Population- Based Study. *PLoS One.* 2012;7(3): e32412.
30. Lawton J, Peel E, Parry O, Douglas M. Patients' perceptions and experiences of taking oral glucose-lowering agents: a longitudinal qualitative study. *Diabet Med.* 2008;25(4):491-5.
31. Wahid R., & Rathinasamy E. V. L. Explore and Develop a Culturally Adopted Behavioral Psycho Educational Family Intervention for Caregivers of Schizophrenic Patients in Egyptian Context. *Journal of Medical Research and Health Sciences.* 2022; 5(2): 1779–1785.